

“THE TIMES” – THE MUSE OF HISTORICAL JUSTICE

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Abstract

“THE TIMES – THE MUSE OF HISTORICAL JUSTICE” discusses the role that the centuries-old British newspaper “TIMES” played in covering the unequal and chaotic battles in the Georgian twenties of the 20th century. It talks of the problems of British colonization of Batumi in the years 1918-1920 and the first terrible years of the Soviet occupation. “THE TIMES” always stood on the side of historical justice and supported Georgia. The articles published in “THE TIMES” show us how the paper tried to expose to the world what was happening in Georgia, and how they could help this small and abandoned country.

Our **field of study** is “THE TIMES” as the evaluator of the history of the 20s in 20th century Georgia and the uncompromising describer of events; The whole role that the paper played in searching for political justice for Georgia.

For our study to have depth and arouse interest, we used a historical and comparative approach, which gave us the opportunity to make logical and objective assessments.

Our **aim** is to study what influence “THE TIMES” had and what trail it left behind in the process of evaluating the Georgian twenties.

On the basis of the materials we have studied, we arrive at the **result** that the role of “THE TIMES” in covering the recent Georgian past is invaluable and does complete justice to all the problems which appeared on the world political map in the twenties.

In the paper, we presented the negative "remnants" of recent history on the example of "THE TIMES" and we came to the conclusion that the newspaper has always been and still remains a muse of historical justice, which is undoubtedly an example of covering the reality of Georgia in the 1920s!

Probably only Paul Valéry could say that history, first of all, is a muse... André Maurois wrote that no one in our era has had such a great influence as this extremely simple person ... (1) so it is like that.

Paul Valéry differently re-evaluated many doubts... feelings... hopes... the earth and a man became "the other" in his hands...

History is indeed a muse, but what a muse consists of, that is the main problem and the essence of the problem too... what his memory stores and why it decides everything.

However, if we believe Bernard Shaw, "one can only learn from the history that people have learned nothing from it..."

What Georgians have learned from their history and what they have not – it is a difficult and controversial issue... maybe, nothing... or – nothing good...

However, there is no doubt that Georgia also has the muses of its history - it suddenly brings out something like it is hard for you to believe that... it is also difficult to realize...

It is difficult to comprehend that exactly 103 years ago - in 1918 - one of the indigenous parts of Georgia - Adjara was occupied by Great Britain...

It is still rarely talked about in Georgia - as if those two years haven't been - from 1918 to 1920 ... as if the independent state of Georgia did not have the occupied territory nearby... As if it was not a tragedy that in 1918 five English ships arrived at the port of Batumi 15,000-20,000 with soldiers... Thus began the "Great Adventure" of the British in Batumi and its regions...

On November 13, 1918, the British Minister of Foreign Affairs decided to occupy Batumi indefinitely - a strategic base for the British navy to provide hostilities on various fronts.

This is how Adjara became another British colony, from where they got gold and jewelry, agricultural products, works of art... Oil bought at a symbolic price (337.5 thousand tons)...

However, we once recalled this story with the famous Georgian director Nana Jorjadze's 1986 film "Robinsoniada, or My English Grandpa", which is about these two years... about these two strange years for Georgia... The film tells the tragic story of the English telegraphist coming from afar... but it is such a romantic story, the occupation is hard to notice... hard to see...

It is as if we spared for Great Britain... as if it was forgiven even for the occupation of Adjara... But history is history by calling everything by its name and nothing can tell us exactly what it was like yesterday, as the main chronicler of mankind - the press...

It is said that the press is also a partisan movement in the back of the state... But it is difficult to say this on the example of Georgia... But if we rely on the main "muse" of the same history of Great Britain - "The Times", we will see a different picture...

Even then - 100 years ago - when, unfortunately, many in Georgia, unfortunately, were seeing the occupation of the Great Britain "romantically", the newspaper "The Times" on February 23, 1920, completely non-romantically assessed the British policy in the Batumi district - "British military power in Batumi took steps that turned out to be wrong: it strengthened the money circulation from Doni in Batumi - instead of the money cycle in Tbilisi (Georgia). Denikin's retreat, of course, caused the money exchange rate of Doni to fall, which also affected the Batumi market; This resulted in rising prices and financial panic, which was also influenced by the red propaganda "(2).

It is symbolic that the letter was published in "The Times" on February 23, 1921... Exactly one year away from the cadet battle against the Soviet Red Army of Georgia at Kojori-Tabakhmela... The brutal defeat of the Georgians, erased even the "memory" of Great Britain and Europe in the Soviet Union, where the 70-year history of the Red Muse began.

But there was a story before that as well - a tangled, complex, but based on some ideas - British-Georgian 2-year history, on which "The Times" also told us - "Our policy in the Transcaucasia has been more or less fruitful lately. The aim of this policy was to establish friendly relations between the Armenian, Tatar, and Georgian republics, although much remains to be done in this regard, but the beginning of this policy was good. But if not the military occupation of Batumi - the western point of the Transcaucasia - our diplomatic steps, as steps in the settlement of these three republics of the fourth neutral party – could not be fruitful "(3).

The article clearly feels the anticipation of something big, very big threat. A breathtaking silence that knows in front of a big noise.

"The Times" is trying to show this threat to the UK... to point to new, dangerous muses of history... and when that threat became real, "The Times" again stubbornly as Don Quixote stood on the side of Georgia, which everyone "forgot"... However, "The Times" stood by us and reached out for the Chairman of the Georgian National Council - Noe Jordania (1868-1953) at the VI International Conference in Genoa...

Our task today is not to assess the historical, political role of Noah Jordan. This is time for other "muses" ... We have to analyze in the "other" context why he went (if he fled) with members of his government to Europe in 1921; To whom did the Junkers throw to and the whole country and why... Obviously, escaping from the danger, he tried to at least give his voice about Georgia to the world; It is through "The Times" that we see Jordania's tragedy; He's a weakness against Sovietized history and "cold-hearted" Europe. "The Times", on the other hand, has never been indifferent to Georgia... That is why it devoted its pages to Noe Jordania on March 21, 1922, who was writing with a heartbreaking sincerity – "If Europe does not speak out against the terrible injustices committed by the Soviet Russian government against Georgia, any

major state will agree to attack neighboring countries and occupy their territories" (5)...

Noe Jordania chooses the right diplomatic course - points to completely different threats to Europe... He knows that only for Georgia the world will not "bother" and will not go against Soviet Russia... of course, He falls into more political romanticism (such a muse has a history...) when he reminds the Genoa International Conference of Article 6 of the Cannes Conference (on the unacceptance of aggression) and kneels down to Europe - "The Georgian people hope that... the great powers, and especially Britain, will demand that the Bolsheviks withdraw their troops from Georgia" (6)...

However, which Georgian people hoped and which big states were worried about the fate of Georgia, it is unclear... History has also confirmed this ambiguity...

"The Times" has always stood on the "bright" side of history and even before the Soviet Union invasion in Georgia was one of the first pointing to the main danger - those familiar with the Bolshevik mentality say that an angry Trotsky could order the army to attack at any cost (7)...

"The Times" (in this case, unfortunately for us) is seldom mistaken ... he was one of the first to confirm in the February 23, 1921 issue of the 11th Army invasion of Georgia...

When you turn the pages of "The Times" in the 1920s, you realize how different the political future of Georgia and the world would be if politicians listened to this newspaper... In fact, it was our voice in the world - the voice of a small, abandoned, powerless country. Which no one remembered and which no one carried as a burden...

"The Times" again stubbornly tried to sensitize the world to Georgia, and on August 15, 1921, wrote: "The Bolsheviks looted the country - food, clothes, shoes, medicine, railroad cars, tram cars, equipment, tools, furniture - they took it all to Russia... People are starving, hospitals are overcrowded, patients are neglected; they have neither medicine nor food. People die of cholera every day (8) ... Most importantly, "The Times" calls for aid to be provided in the way "to prevent it from falling into the hands of the Bolsheviks who have thrown Georgia into this difficult day" (9).

Therefore, "The Times", realizing that there was no hope for the world's political leaders, almost launched the People's movement to save Georgia and the Georgian people. It's not well-known how the world engaged in this "stubbornness" but obviously - it, as the media, as the muse of the justice of history, stood by us in the most difficult times and in the most difficult situations.

"The Times" kept its historical mark!

But the "the other" was the political vision of Great Britain itself... Moreover, by the decision of the British government, a commercial agreement was signed and the credit was allocated to the Soviet Union...

Scottish MP Walter Elliott described the incident in "The Times" on September 27, 1924, as a crime against a small Caucasian state... as a murder of Georgia... The British government was "shocked" by such an assessment. A "cautious" resolution was also submitted to the Association - to monitor developments of the events in Georgia and restore peace... However, something else was happening... The resolution was a democratic formality and nothing else... It was reaffirmed in 1924 after the uprising for the restoration of Georgia's national-state independence. After the uprising... The uprising was brutally suppressed by the Bolsheviks, of course... A few months after the bloody revenge, a delegation of the British Labor Party visited Georgia...

"The Times" keeps the humiliating secret of this visit... The report of the delegation's trip was published here on February 28, 1925 - the British Labor Party described Georgia as a "happy country"... only the restriction of freedom of speech by the Soviet authorities was rejected... only the restriction of freedom of speech... "The Guardian" newspaper called this report the most shameful attempt to embellish the truth... The article also shows that the British government knew exactly what happened in Georgia in 1924... Long before the delegation's visit to Russia, there was convincing material in London. "The Guardian," wrote about the slaughterhouse organized by Moscow and its butchers in Georgia.

It is true that "The Times" could not change the historical justice in Georgia, but it kept all the trifles, all the details of the terrible period when the country, which was barely visible on the map, was abandoned and rejected by the whole world...

Proved that the world is in political "debt" to Georgia...

It is said that history is silent on many stories, but in Europe, which has 236 years (since 1785) has its time, its "The Times", it is difficult to keep silent about stories... This is what "The Times" is a symbol of world pulse - do not miss anything on the side of justice ... to remain the muse of historical justice ... This is indisputable on the example of Georgia in the 1920s!

And if history is a terrible judgment of the ancestors, then "The Times" is one of the main judges of the historical chaos, which is called the recent past...

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